

AIMC 2024 (09/09 - 11/09)

glemöhnic

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glemöhnic

Project Description

glemöhnic is a ~20 minute performance piece that utilises SpeechBrain, OpenAI and CoquiTTS voice and speech models to transcribe, synthesise and clone historical and real-time improvised vocal gestures.

This piece explores how extra-normal [1] vocal sounds trigger and provoke nonsensical AI-mediations of human vocality, by utilising non-text audio as input material for text-expectant AI speech recognition and synthesis models. The mediation of non-textual human voice gestures by these ASR models yields eclectic, bizarre and poetic nonsense, which is further utilised as textual input for text-to-speech synthesis and voice cloning models. CoquiTTS' [2] XTTS_V2 model re-constructs the syllabic, phonemic and garbled poems into vocal clones that oscillate between their reference audio (the original audio dataset input) and the scraped audio data that the XTTS_V2 model has been trained on. The result of this is a collection of original and cloned audio samples that are utilised as sonic material in a live coded musical performance, using the [strudelREPL](#) platform.

To give a specific overview of how the AI model pipeline is implemented in *glemöhnic*, [Image 1](#) below illustrates the overall flow for the models used, and will be systematically discussed.

Image 1
Outline of the model pipeline for *glemöhnic*

manipulation is to engage with a form of AI voice *to* construct sound collages inspired by Dada [6][7][8], grounded within rhythmic and gestural conventions of improvised voice.

Thematically, *glemöhnic* engages with the conference theme in its engagement of AI models that have been built, trained and deployed with certain intentionalities: namely to recognise, transcribe and synthesis human speech. It further ties into sound art exploration, historical art movements around language and text-as-sound (such as Dada and *zaum*).

Type of submission

glemöhnic would work best in Performance 2 at Oxford University. It could also work well at the Performance 3 club night at the Old Fire Station, as it utilises the strudel live coding platform to interact with the output XTTS cloned audio.

Technical/Stage Requirements

The performer will provide:

- own laptop
- microphones
- audio transmitter and receiver pack
- audio interface
- power plugs and UK power adaptors.

The performer can also bring all of her own audio cable, if required. The audio interface has two female XLR outputs, one for each stereo channel, which should go to the PA system.

The following is also required:

- a standing-height table that would suitably fit a laptop, audio interface, the transmitter and receiver
- stereo PA system (ideally with subwoofer) and basic theatrical lighting.

Program Notes

What secrets and poetry might be contained in our burps? Our giggles?

glemöhnic utilises explores how our vocal identities are pulled from us, and reformed into new vocal identities- through feeding a sigh or cough into text-oriented AI voice models and allowing them to unravel and warp.

This performance utilises open sourced speech recognition models from SpeechBrain, OpenAI and CoquiTTS to transcribe, synthesise, clone and mutate real-time vocal sounds and historical voice datasets. From this unraveling of non-text voice sounds by text-expectant AI models, scraped and forgotten voices are sung into

being and rise from the dusty depths of scraped datasets. These new sounding bodies are reunited with their parent voice bodies, to create converging and diverging tapestries inspired by Dada and *zaum*.

glemöhnic catalyses the wayward mutations of human voice that occur when wordless voice is fed to word-dependent AI models.

Media

```
(itmts) C:\Users\kelse\Documents\ITMTS>python miniasr.py
File "C:\Users\kelse\Documents\ITMTS\miniasr.py", line 3
    audio = 'C:\Users\kelse\Documents\ITMTS\test.wav'
                                                ^
SyntaxError: (unicode error) 'unicodeescape' codec can't decode bytes

(itmts) C:\Users\kelse\Documents\ITMTS>python miniasr.py
C:\Anaconda\envs\itmts\Lib\site-packages\whisper\transcribe.py:115: Us
  warnings.warn("FP16 is not supported on CPU; using FP32 instead")
  快點點點旁極 The future

(itmts) C:\Users\kelse\Documents\ITMTS>python miniasr.py
C:\Anaconda\envs\itmts\Lib\site-packages\whisper\transcribe.py:115: Us
  warnings.warn("FP16 is not supported on CPU; using FP32 instead")
  Do do do do do do do did it by by by test test

(itmts) C:\Users\kelse\Documents\ITMTS>python recorder.py
Recording... 🎧
🎧
🎧
🎧
🎧
🎧
```

Image 3

Screenshot taken during a session generating glemöhnic samples

```

8 d: 'OG/118-spoken_text_gain@/-190430_1/23-021.wav',
9 e: 'OG/fry/34-vocal fry-190516_2015-glued-04.wav',
10 f: 'TTS/34-vocal fry-190516_2015-glued-04_TTS_output.wav'
11
12 }, 'github: [REDACTED]/sounds');
13
14 // hellooooo
15
16 // i hope you're ready to hear my voice again
17
18 // strudel hide-console
19 stack(
20
21 s_["f"]
22 .gain("<0.0145 0.145 >")
23 .color('grey'),
24
25 s("e ~ e")
26 .gain("<0.145 >") //fuckkkk louddddd- she (is me) is traumatiseddd.
27 .early(0.4)
28 // .struct("x x")
29 // .echo(2, 1/8, .6)
30 // // .pan("0.5")
31 // .adsr(~0.1:1:5:0.2")
32 // .slow(1)
33 // .jux(rev)
34 .color 'red',

```

Image 4

Screenshot taken during a live coding session with glemöhnic samples

Some smaller audio excerpts are included below, as demonstration.

Audio 3

Smaller excerpt from glemöhnic

Audio 4

Smaller excerpt from glemöhnic

Audio 5

Smaller excerpt from glemöhnic

Artist Biography

[Kelsey Cotton](#) is a vocalist-artist-mover working with experimental music, Musical Artificial Intelligence, electronic textiles, soft-robotics, and Human-Computer Interaction. As a researcher, Kelsey is fascinated with pushing the limits of musical bodies, with her recent work delving deeper into designing artifacts which harness, augment and fuse different physiologies. She is passionate about somatic interaction, the potential for intersomatic experiences between fleshy and synthetic bodies, and first-person feminist perspectives of musical AI. Kelsey is currently undertaking PhD studies in Interactive Music and AI at Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg, Sweden.

Ethics Statement

The paper has utilised open-sourced, pretrained AI models and the first author's own personal dataset. No human participants (other than the first author) were recruited for this study, and no sensitive data were collected. This paper has the intention to contribute to musical AI research, and to support future research within this community. The predicted environmental impact of this work as minimal since the computation required to create this work was comparable to daily personal computer usage. Accessibility of the technology in this work is limited with the general accessibility to computers and computational development frameworks.

Acknowledgements

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Footnotes

1. If multiple audio files are called, or multiple live gestures are recorded in quick succession ↵

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